
Assessment of Teacher Educators' Level of Awareness of Artificial Intelligence Tools for Teaching in Tertiary Institutions

By

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Abstract

The study was to assess teachers' educators' level of awareness of Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools for teaching in tertiary institutions in Nigeria. One research question and one hypothesis guided the study. Descriptive survey research design was employed. The population comprised all 1,032 teacher educators in faculty of Education in tertiary institutions in Imo state. The sample is made up 602 teachers Educators using propionate sampling technique. Data was collected using questionnaire titled Teachers Educators Awareness AI Tools in Teaching (TEAATT). The questionnaire was validated by an expert in Measurement and Evaluation. The reliability coefficient of 0.81 was established using Cronbach Alpha. Mean and Standard Deviation were used to answer the research questions while chi-square was used in hypotheses testing. Findings from the study showed that lecturers are aware of application of AI in teaching processes in tertiary institutions in Nigeria. It also shows that; they have positive perception in adopting AI in teaching tertiary institutions in Nigeria. The study recommended the that, universities administrators should organize workshops, training sessions and online courses to deepen lecturers' knowledge and understanding of AI tools and how they can be effectively applied in teaching.

Key words: Assessment, Awareness, Artificial Intelligence, Teaching and Tertiary Institutions

Introduction

The tertiary institution is a higher institution of learning established with the tasked of preparing graduates to earn degrees in a range of disciplines. It offers a variety of academic programs and courses to help students become experts in their chosen professions. In addition, it fosters the development of critical thinking, problem-solving, and communication abilities in the students. Lecturers are those who impart knowledge to students in the universities and in order to guarantee comprehensive learning, they play a variety of task such as mentoring, supervising, and assisting the students. Masaazi (2015) defines a teachers Educator as a facilitator who helps the student comprehend the material being taught as well as carryout assessment to determine the extent or how much of what is learnt by the students, to measure the extent of students' proficiency, regular assessment is necessitated through examinations.

According to Filsecker and Kerres (2012), educational assessment refers to a variety of instruments, methods, or processes that are employed to gauge and appraise learning results, output, or advancement in scholarly, professional, medical, or alternative settings. According to Madu and Musa (2024), assessments play crucial role in measuring students' skills and establishing a supportive learning environment. It shows the strengths, limitations, and learning styles of the students. These, the lecturers do by using various experience they were exposed to. Nevertheless, traditional method of assessing students is traditional methods to gauge the extent the students have learnt from the teaching learning becoming ineffective due to rapid increase in students' population. The adoption and application of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in teaching of students could be useful in this situation.

AI is the use of computers and other devices to perform tasks that are associated with and resemble those of humans. Russell and Norvig (2016) defined AI as machines that replicate human cognitive capabilities such as learning, comprehension, reasoning, or problem-solving. Also, according to Farrokhnia, Banihashem, Noroozi and Wals (2023), AI is the science and engineering of creating systems that are capable of performing tasks commonly associated with intelligent beings such as learning, judgment, and decision-making. AI has enormous promise for personalizing learning, automating administrative processes, and improving the overall teaching and learning process. This potential has been sparked by the technology's rapid development and implementation in a variety of fields, including education. It has however been observed that most teachers do not make use of AI as observed by some researchers. Researches conducted worldwide, including in Nigeria, indicate that a large number of teachers are not well-versed in AI and its potential uses, which makes it difficult to effectively use AT in the classroom (Gaber et al., 2023) In 2023, Kundariya identified the top AI tools for enhancing academic research, including Semantic Scholar, IBM Watson, Scholarcy, Elicit, Trinka, Google Scholar, Scite, Tablea, Mendeley, Consensus, and Zotero. In the same year, Barua identified additional AI tools, including SciSpace, Schoaricy, Jenni AI, ChatGPT, Paperpal, Casper, Grammarly, QuiltBot, Elicit, Turnitin, Consensus, Search Smart, Mendeley, and Evidence Hunt. Okuonghae and Tunmibi (2024) categorized digital competency into the following areas. The advantages of using AI in teaching and learning processes are therefore enormous.

The utilization of AI in teaching has remained low according to some studies. For instance, research conducted by Nchunge, Sakwa, and Mwanga (2013) showed that most lecturers in higher institutions have accustomed themselves with nearly obsolete systems, making it difficult for them to fully utilize the educational potential of emerging technologies. Sife, Lwoga and Sanga as cited in Bamidele (2019), advance several reasons while there is

low level of adoption of AI in teaching and learning in many developing countries. These include socioeconomic and technological challenges such as lack of a system approach to learning, administrative and technical support, staff development, and lack of ownership, inadequate funds, awareness, perception and attitudes towards AI.

Awareness indicates the extent to which users have information and knowledge of AI. Amadi-Iwai, Ubulom and Okiridu (2024) define awareness as knowledge about something that exists or understanding of a situation or subject at the present time based on information or experience. This could be seen as a knowledge or perception of a situation, fact, consciousness, recognition, realization, grasp and acknowledgement concern about and well-informed interest or familiarity in a particular situation or development based on this definition. Perception on the other hand has been defined as the entirety of our attitudes toward things or ourselves; a set of ideas that one holds about things, views that are relatively hard to change (Ibrahim, 2014). This is why the researchers began to wonder if the lecturers are aware of AI and also have positive perception towards the adoption of AI in teaching and assessment processes. The reason being that before utilization of a thing, one should even be aware of it, the worry of the researchers. Therefore, it involves identification and is the recognition and interpretation of the signals that the brain gets from the sense organs.

Wohlwill (2017) asserts that behavioral and central determinants, such as needs, experiences, rewards, and values, have an impact on perception. Individual differences in the prevalence of these qualities lead to unequal perception. An individual cannot have all of their information processed and used at once. An actual selecting process exists in the selection of the processed information to be used. According to Ibrahim and Saleh (2020), the receiver's higher-order or general knowledge and perception of the context influence what is chosen and how categories are laid up. Put another way, perception is impacted by conceptually driven input (what one knows) but also receives data-driven input (external stimuli). Undoubtedly, AI has been ingrained in the educational industry, raising significant concerns about ethics, equity, and the fundamental structure of evaluation procedures.

While ChatGPT and other AI-powered technologies are efficient and accessible, Rudolph, Tan and Tan (2023) highlighted a critical issue about students using AI to outsource their written assignments. There is a real concern that creativity and critical thinking abilities may decline, which has led to a reassessment of AI's potential to enhance rather than replace student learning. Additionally, there is debate on the effectiveness and consistency of AI tests, especially when it comes to identifying subtle aspects of writing like originality and coherence (Aluthman, 2016). This calls into question how best to strike a balance between the comprehensive insights provided by human evaluators and automated methods. The study by Luckin (2017) illuminates the possible advantages of these technologies with regard to AI-enabled adaptive and continuous assessment. Strong proof of their long-term effects, however still remains a gap in current research.

Gaber et al. (2023) examined AI awareness among faculty members at King Faisal University and its relationship with Technology Acceptance (TA) and Digital Competencies (DCs). The results showed a medium level of awareness, with no significant relationship between AI awareness and TA. Nonetheless, it was discovered that DCs and AI awareness were positively correlated. The report recommends enhancing perceptions of AI and training educators to apply it in the classroom. Biriemiokhale and Sulyman (2023) conducted a study on awareness and perceptions of AI among 37 professional librarians in Kwara State, Nigeria. They found that respondents were aware of Chatbots and Dynamed, and believed AI could replace human librarians in the future. They perceived AI as beneficial for providing patron-

tailored recommendations, reducing manual tasks, and facilitating knowledge discovery. However, poor internet connectivity and lack of expertise among librarians were major factors affecting AI adoption.

In a study conducted by Amadi-Iwal, Ubulom, and Okiridu (2024) to ascertain the awareness, competence and utilization of AI for improved job performance by Business Educators in universities in south-south Nigeria indicated a lack of knowledge of AI. The research findings indicate that business educators lack sufficient proficiency in utilizing AI in teaching. Agarry, Omolafe, Animashaun, and Babalola, (2022) also investigated the primary education undergraduates' competency in the use of AI for learning. The findings of the study were that majority of the primary education undergraduates were not skilled and incompetent in the use of AI for learning. Abayomi, Adenekan, Abayomi, Ajayi, and Aderonke, (2020) investigated the awareness and perception about AI in the management of university libraries in Nigeria. The finding of the study revealed that academic librarians were aware of the existence of AI usage in the university libraries and that the fear of job loss is the major constraint they face in the adoption of the technologies; even though they are aware that the innovative technologies will enable efficient user satisfaction.

Madu and Musa (2024) investigated lecturers' level of awareness of AI as correlate of their digital competency in Federal University, Wukari (FUW) reported that there was moderate level of awareness of lecturers on AI, and also there was positive relationship between lecturers' level of awareness of AI and their digital competence, among others.

Theoretically, this study is centered on the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), which was proposed by Fred Davis in 1989. According to this model, perceived usefulness (PU) and perceived ease of use (PEOU) are the two main determinants of a person's decision to embrace and employ technology. PU refers to the extent to which an individual believes that utilizing a specific technology will improve their performance at work. PEOU measures an individual's belief that a specific technology will be effortless to use. The likelihood of adoption increases with the degree to which users believe these technologies are simple to use. Factors such as institutional support, training and infrastructures play a role in lecturers' acceptance of AI in universities in Nigeria. The applicability of the theory lies in the belief that lecturers' perception of the usefulness of a technology in improving their teaching and assessment will motivate them to adopt AI.

It is evident from literature review that there exists a significant research gap regarding lecturers' level of AI awareness and perception of its adoption as a tool for teaching and learning in universities in Nigeria. The reviewed studies explored AI awareness and utilization in various fields, among various populations of interest and within the university community in Nigeria. However, none focused specifically on lecturers at universities in Nigeria. For instance, Amadi-Iwai et al. (2024) investigated educators in south-south Nigeria and Madu and Musa (2024) investigated Lecturers in FUW. However, the context of these institutions, its faculty demographics, and existing technology infrastructure cannot be claimed to be the same in all universities in Nigeria.

Studies by Agarry et al. (2022) and Amadi-Iwai et al. (2024) highlight a competence gap in utilizing AI for learning and teaching. However, the link between awareness and the perception of lecturers in adopting it was not explored. This study aims to fill this gap by systematically assessing lecturers' awareness and perceptions, identifying the factors that influence these perceptions, and exploring the barriers to adoption. By providing empirical evidence on these aspects, the study seeks to inform the development of targeted

interventions to promote the effective use of AI tools in higher education, ultimately enhancing teaching practices and learning outcomes.

The rapid advancement of AI has significantly impacted various sectors, including education. AI tools have the potential to transform teaching and assessment practices, offering benefits such as personalized learning, efficient grading, and enhanced instructional support. However, the successful integration of AI in higher education largely depends on the awareness and perception of university lecturers, who are the primary agents of implementation. Despite the growing availability and potential advantages of AI tools, there is a concern that many university lecturers may lack sufficient awareness of these technologies and their applications. Furthermore, even when lecturers are aware of AI tools, their perceptions regarding the adoption of these technologies can vary widely. Negative perceptions, driven by concerns about data privacy, reliability, and the complexity of AI tools, can hinder their adoption and effective use in educational settings.

Currently, there is limited empirical research examining the extent of university lecturers' awareness and their perceptions of AI tools for teaching and assessment. Without a clear understanding of these factors, educational institutions may struggle to develop effective strategies for AI tool adoption, training, and support. This study aims to fill this gap by assessing the level of awareness and perception of AI tools among university lecturers. By identifying the factors that influence these perceptions and the barriers to adoption, the study seeks to provide insights that can inform the development of targeted interventions to promote the effective use of AI in higher education. This, in turn, can lead to improved teaching practices and enhanced learning outcomes for students.

Research Question

To assess teacher Educators' level of awareness of AI tools for teaching in tertiary institutions in Nigeria, the following research question was answered:

1. What is teacher educators' level of awareness of AI for teaching in tertiary institutions in Imo state?

Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design to assess teacher educators' level of awareness of Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools for teaching in tertiary institutions in Imo State. According to Maduakonam (2022), descriptive survey research seeks to collect detailed factual information that describes the nature of existing conditions. It assesses the characteristics of the whole population and usually study sample drawn from the population of the study. The population comprised all 1,032 teacher educators in faculty of Education in tertiary institutions in Imo state. The sample is made up 602 teachers Educators using propionate sampling technique. Data was collected using questionnaire titled Teachers Educators awareness AI Tools in Teaching (TEAATT). The questionnaire was validated by an expert in Measurement and Evaluation. The reliability coefficient of 0.81 was established using Cronbach Alpha. Data were analyzed using mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions while chi-square was used in hypotheses testing.

Results

Research Question One: What are the of Teacher Educators level of awareness of Artificial Intelligence tools for teaching in tertiary institutions.

Table 1: Mean scores and Standard Deviation analysis of level of awareness of Artificial Intelligence tools for teaching.

s/n	Items	Mean	SD	Remarks
1	Turnitin (plagiarism detection)	3.00	1.0	Aware
2	Grammarly (writing assistance)	2.95	0.9	Aware
3	Coursera (online courses and resources)	3.00	1.0	Aware
4	Khan Academy	2.89	0.8	Aware
5	Moodle	3.00	1.0	Aware
6	AI chatbots	2.80	0.8	Aware
7	AI-driven analytics	2.78	0.6	Aware

Table 1 shows that items 1 to 7 have mean scores above the cut-off point of 2.50. This shows that teacher educators are aware of application of AI tools for teaching in tertiary institutions.

Hypothesis One: teacher educators' level of awareness of Artificial Intelligence for teaching in tertiary institutions in Nigeria is not significant

Table 2: Chi square test of significance of teacher educators' level of awareness of Artificial Intelligence for teaching in tertiary institutions in Nigeria.

	N	Df	X ²	sig.	Alpha Level	Remark
Pearson Chi - Rejected Square	556	21	226.309	.000	0.05	Significant

P%,000) <0,05. N- Number, Df- Degree of freedom, X²=Chi-square calculated, Sig=p-value: P<,05.

Table 2 shows chi-square analysis on lecturers' level of awareness of Artificial Intelligence for teaching and assessment in universities in Nigeria. The Table reveals x of 226.309, the significant value (P-value) of 0.000 and the degree of freedom of 21. Since 0.000 (P-value) is < 0.05 (Alpha value), the difference is significant. This implies that lecturers are aware of using Artificial Intelligence for teaching and assessment in universities in Nigeria.

Hence, the null hypothesis which states that lecturers' level of awareness of Artificial Intelligence for teaching and assessment in universities in Nigeria is not significant was rejected.

Discussion of Findings

It was revealed from the study that lecturers are aware of using Artificial Intelligence (AI) for teaching and assessment in universities in Nigeria. This is because according to information from the study, AI tools can be utilized in detecting plagiarism as well as monitoring of students' performance. This finding agrees with the findings of Abayomi, Adenekan, Abayomi, Ajayi and Aderonke, (2020) who investigated the awareness and perception about AI in the management of university libraries in Nigeria and found that academic librarians were aware of the existence of AI usage in the university libraries; they were also aware that the innovative technologies will enable efficient user satisfaction.

In the same vein, Madu and Musa (2024) investigated lecturers' level of awareness of AI as correlate of their digital competency in Federal University, Wukari (FUW) reported that there was moderate level of awareness of lecturers on AI. However, the finding of the study is at variance with the study by Amadi-Iwai, Ubulom, and Okiridu (2024) to ascertain the awareness, competence and utilization of AI for improved job performance by Business Educators in universities in South-South Nigeria found that Business Educators lack sufficient proficiency in utilizing AI in teaching. The result, as found in this current study could be as a result of the increase in emphasis on technology in teaching and learning, and other professional development opportunities that have made lecturers to be aware of using AI in teaching and assessment. The finding could also be attributed to the knowledge lecturers gained in educational webinars on AI they have attended.

Conclusion

Based on the findings from the study, the integration of AI-driven tools and methods by teacher educators in tertiary institutions in Nigeria will enhance teaching and assessment processes. It will lead to improved learning experiences for students, greater efficiency in administrative tasks, and the potential for more personalized education. Lecturers' positive perception of utilizing AI tools in teaching and assessment suggests that they have threat to their roles.

Recommendations

In view of the findings and conclusion of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Universities administrators should organize workshops, training sessions and online courses to deepen lecturers' knowledge and understanding of AI tools and how they can be effectively applied in teaching and assessment. This is because lecturers' been aware of AI does not translate to practical knowledge and hands-on experience in effective integration of AI in pedagogical practices.
2. Universities administrators should provide lecturers with access to AI-powered teaching tools, assessment platforms, and learning management systems that integrate AI features. This is because, even though lecturers have a high perception of AI, they may not always have the necessary tools or resources to adopt or use it in teaching and assessment processes. Thus, ensuring easy access will help translate their positive perception into practical application.

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